

THERMAL ANALYSIS OF RESISTANCE WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a transient finite element model for thermal analysis of resistance welding of thermoplastic composites with metal mesh heating element. The model assumes an orthotropic thermal behaviour of the composite laminate. Different types of material and welding configurations were analysed. The transient temperature profiles were computed using temperature independent properties. The results were compared with experimental data from the performed measurements, and they showed a close agreement. The study was mainly focused on the combined influence of the material properties and the process parameters on the occurrence of the edge effect and its impact on the temperature profiles at the edges of the specimens. Additionally, the influence of the insulating material on the temperature profiles in the weld were studied and discussed.

KEYWORDS: thermal analysis, resistance welding, heat transfer, thermoplastic composites.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the growing need for high performance applications, continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites are becoming of greater interest for the industry in recent years. The greater interest results in the development of more complex structures, which makes joining the critical step in their production [1]. Fusion bonding, also known as welding, is considered to be an ideal technique for joining thermoplastic composites [2]. It is a technique developed specifically for thermoplastic materials that uses their main characteristic, the possibility to be subsequently melted and cooled while retaining their properties, to form the joint. The welding process can be simply described as joining of two parts by fusing their contact interfaces, followed by cooling (consolidating) under pressure, which enables the bond to be made [3]. The schematic view of the welding process is shown in Fig. 1.

From the large amount of available welding techniques, resistance welding is considered to be one of the most promising [4]. The heat to the interface is provided by electrically resistant heating element that remains trapped in the joint after the welding. The main advantages of the resistance welding are very simple, low cost tooling [5] and little or no surface treatment [6]. The fact that the heating element remains in the weld offers the possibility of reprocessing if inspection shows flaws or incomplete bonding [6,7].

Modelling resistance welding is of essential importance for the rapid development and optimisation of the process. Modelling has become an indispensable step in determining the values of the processing parameters, improving by that the efficiency of the optimisation process and reducing the high costs of experimental testing procedures [4]. Modelling the

heat transfer is the first step in modelling the resistance welding process. Heat transfer models predict the temperature profiles in the welding stack, providing by that the input for further modelling of the consolidation, crystallization and the quality of the weld. Several heat transfer models were developed by various groups of researchers. Mafezzoli et al. developed a one-dimensional (1D) heat transfer model as a part of a mathematical model for describing the welding process of PEEK-carbon fibre laminates [8]. Jakobsen et al. [9] and Xiao et al. [10] proposed a transient two-dimensional (2D) thermal model for resistance welding of anisotropic thermoplastic composites. Holmes and Gillespie developed 1D and 2D numerical thermal models for the resistance welding of large-scale components [11]. Ageorges et al. developed a transient three-dimensional (3D) finite element thermal model for resistance welding [12].

This paper presents a thermal analysis of resistance welding of thermoplastic

Fig. 1: Schematic view of the welding configuration.

composites. 2D and 3D finite element thermal models have been developed and employed for performing the analysis. Transient temperature profiles in the weld were computed and compared with experimental data for validation. The focus of the investigation was on the temperature profiles at the edges of the weld. The influence of the edge effect on the overall temperature uniformity was investigated. Additionally, the influence of the insulation material and its thickness on the temperature profiles through the weld thickness was investigated.

MODELLING

A finite element heat transfer model was developed to perform the thermal analysis of the welding process. The model was evaluated in two versions, 2D and 3D, which produced mostly identical results, due to the chosen geometry of the welded specimens. The finite element model was generated, solved and post-processed using FEMLAB, version 3.1. Standard built-in meshing routine used for meshing the geometry gave results with satisfactory accuracy. The geometry of the model was based on the standard double cantilever beam (DCB) welding configuration that was used for obtaining the experimental data [13], schematically shown in Fig.1. The material used in this study was continuous glass and carbon fibre reinforced polyetherimide (GF/PEI and CF/PEI). The specimens used for obtaining the experimental data were 200 mm long and 25 mm wide, cut from a fully consolidated 8-ply laminates, received from the supplier, Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands. The laminates were 2 mm thick, with quasi-isotropic $[\pm 45/0/90]$ configuration. A stainless steel mesh (wire diameter 0.2 mm, gap 0.86 mm and mesh thickness 0.4 mm) was chosen as a material for manufacturing the heating element. In order to provide a resin rich

content in the bonding surface, as well as to prevent the entrapment of air in the mesh, the mesh was impregnated between two 100 μm thick resin layers (PEI films).

The model geometry is schematically shown in Fig.2. Thermal symmetry was used to

Fig. 2: Schematic view of the model geometry (not in scale, all dimensions in mm).

minimize the computational time, which resulted in the model geometry representing one eighth of the global one (100 mm long and 12.5 mm wide). The heating element was modelled as a homogeneous and isotropic stainless-steel stripe (0.4 mm thick), and the heating was assumed uniform [7]. The Joule heating within the heating element was simulated as a volumetric heat generation correspondent to the applied input power level. The neat resin film (0.1 mm thick) used for impregnating the heating element was modelled as a separate layer of isotropic material. The composite laminates (with thickness of 2 mm) were assumed homogeneous and orthotropic. The longitudinal and transversal heat transfer coefficients were computed using the rule of mixtures:

$$k_L = k_{Lf}v_f + k_m v_m \quad (1)$$

$$k_T = \frac{k_m k_{Tf}}{k_m v_f + k_{Tf} v_m} \quad (2)$$

where k_L -longitudinal thermal conductivity of the prepreg; k_{Lf} -longitudinal fibre thermal conductivity; k_m -conductivity of the resin material; k_T -transverse conductivity of the prepreg; k_{Tf} -transversal fibre thermal conductivity and v_f, v_m -volume fractions of the fibres and the matrix respectively. The insulation block was also part of the model geometry, its thickness varying with the type of insulating material used. The values of the material properties used in the thermal analysis are given in Table 1. The properties of the GF/PEI and CF/PEI laminates were calculated according to the rule of mixtures (Eqn. 1) using the material properties of the fibres and the PEI matrix.

From a heat transfer point of view, the resistance welding process is a typical heat conduction process. The convection and radiation heat transfer modes are present only on the boundaries. At the lines/planes of symmetry a thermal insulation (zero heat flux) condition was applied. Convective and radiative losses were assigned to the areas of the welding stack and the heating element (when the edge effect was evaluated) that were exposed to the environment. The convective losses to the environment were modelled as free convection to the ambient air, with a convective heat transfer coefficient of 5 $\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ and constant ambient temperature of 21°C. The assigned radiative losses to the exposed area of the heating element

were computed using constant emissivity of 95%. The constant volume heat generation was applied at time zero with a smoothing term in the first two seconds in order to simulate the start of the process more realistically.

Table 1: The material properties used in the thermal model.

<i>Material</i>	k_{xx} [W/mK]	k_{yy}/k_{zz} [W/mK]	ρ [kg/m ³]	c_p [J/kgK]
HDF Wood	0.17	0.17	5400	2400
Stainless Steel	10	10	7780	460
PEI	0.22	0.22	1270	1248
GF/PEI	0.614	0.614	1904	1042
CF/PEI	4.61	0.29	1527	1272

THERMAL ANALYSIS

The thermal analysis was based on the computed temperature profiles along the weld length, width and most importantly, through the thickness of the weld. Model predictions were validated by comparing them to the data from experimentally obtained temperature data [13]. Transient temperature was monitored using a set of 6 type-K thermocouples, fully insulated and connected to a data acquisition system. The acquisition rate for each measurement point was one data per second. Thermal history at the weld interface of a GF/PEI DCB specimen for an intermediate power level of 80 KW/m² is shown in Fig. 3. The computed results showed good agreement with the experimental data, despite the fact that the temperature profiles were calculated using temperature independent material properties.

Fig. 3: Comparison between the experimental data and the computed thermal histories for GF/PEI with power level of 80 KW/m².

The influence of the material properties on the temperature profiles was investigated in the first part of the study. The temperature profiles through the weld thickness of the glass fibre and carbon fibre laminates were compared. The results for a power level of 80 KW/m^2 and welding time of 60 seconds are shown in Fig. 4. The temperature reached at the CF/PEI weld interface was significantly higher than the temperature at the GF/PEI weld interface. Furthermore, the CF/PEI temperature profiles through the weld thickness were spread in a wider range compared to those of GF/PEI. As a result, higher temperature gradients were predicted through the thickness of the CF/PEI weld, while GF/PEI showed more uniform heating through the weld thickness. These differences in the temperature distribution are a direct consequence of the different thermal properties of the welded materials, most notably their heat transfer coefficients. As it can be seen in Table 1, the heat transfer coefficient of GF/PEI has roughly double the value of the transversal heat transfer coefficient of CF/PEI. This leads to a much slower progress of the heat front through the thickness of the CF/PEI weld, resulting in higher temperatures at the weld interface and sharper thermal gradients. It should also be noted that the longitudinal heat transfer coefficient of the CF/PEI, which has extremely high value compared to the transversal one, does not improve the heat transfer due to the geometry of the weld, where the heat front advances through the thickness of the weld, in the transversal direction.

Fig. 4: Through-thickness temperature profiles for a) CF/PEI and b) GF/PEI welding configuration.

The general conclusion was that composite materials with low transversal heat conductivity offer the opportunity of local heat-up in the vicinity of the heating element, especially for high power levels. Materials with higher transversal conductivity, on the other hand, provide more uniform heating of the bulk material. These conclusions can be used for tailoring the welding process according to the material properties and application requirements.

The Edge Effect

A uniform temperature distribution on the contact surface of the welded parts is of essential importance for achieving a successful weld. A uniform temperature distribution, coupled with a uniform pressure along the weld would produce a bond with uniform strength along its length, which is the ultimate goal of the development of a bonding technique. However, the main phenomenon during welding with a standard weld configuration, shown in Fig.1, is the occurrence of severe temperature non-uniformity close to the edges of the weld, known as the

edge effect. It is believed to be a result of the poor heat transfer by natural convection from the part of the heating element exposed to open air (denoted as “b” in Fig. 2) as opposed to the one inside the weld. This difference leads to severe thermal gradients and rapid melt front propagation in that area. It is also considered as one of the major limiting factors for enlarging the welding area [7,12].

Fig. 5: The edge-effect temperature profiles along the weld line and through weld thickness for GF/PEI.

The focus of this analysis was mainly set on studying the edge effect. The influence of the composite material properties and welding parameters on the temperature distribution was investigated, as well as the influence of the edge effect on the maximum weld length. Temperature profiles were computed for both GF/PEI and CF/PEI configurations with varying energy inputs and model geometry (length of the heating element exposed to open air “b”).

The temperature profiles for GF/PEI configuration, at a power level of 80 KW/m² and the length of the heating element in open air b=10 mm, are plotted in Fig. 5. The edge effect in this case was concentrated relatively close to the edge of the weld, with constant temperature profiles starting already from the point 15 mm from the edge. From that point on, the temperature along the length of the weld remained constant. The limited penetration of the

Fig. 6: The edge-effect temperature profiles along the weld line and through weld thickness for CF/PEI.

edge effect led to high concentration of heat input in this area that resulted in very sharp thermal gradients. The limited penetration of the edge effect was ascribed to the low conductivity of the GF/PEI laminate, which combined with its relatively small thickness does not allow the heat flux to penetrate deeper into the material. The influence of the heat conductivity is also clearly visible in the case of CF/PEI welding configuration, whose temperature profiles at the same welding conditions are plotted in Fig. 6. Due to much higher longitudinal conductivity of the CF/PEI laminate (eight times the conductivity of GF/PEI), the heat flux was able to penetrate much deeper into the material along the weld length. In this case, the uniform temperature profiles start at 25-30 mm from the edge of the weld. As a consequence of larger heat dissipation in the material, the thermal gradients generated by the edge effect in this configuration were more moderate compared to the gradients generated in the GF/PEI configuration.

Changing the welding parameters and the geometry of the welding stack did not lead to considerable changes in the penetration depth of the edge effect. Welding with higher power levels produced same thermal gradient (the temperature difference between the weld edge and the weld interior remained the same, 200°C for GF/PEI configuration and 150°C for CF/PEI configuration). Although the penetration depth did not increase, the time needed for the temperature at the edges of the weld to reach the material degradation point decreased significantly. Increasing the length of the heating element exposed to open air (length “b” in Fig. 1.), on the other hand, did not produce any remarkable change in the thermal profile of the welding stack.

It was concluded that the edge effect in itself does not restrict the welding area (welding length), seeing that it affects only the temperature in a limited area in the vicinity of the weld edges. The thermal gradients that it produces at the edges can however, under certain conditions prevent the completion of the weld.

Fig. 7: The influence of the insulation material on the thermal profiles in the weld.

The Influence of the Insulation Material

The influence of the insulation material on the temperature distribution was investigated by computing the temperature distribution for three different insulating materials: HDF wood, silicone rubber and steel. Welding parameters were the same as in the rest of the study: medium power level of 80 KW/m² and welding time of 60 sec. The temperature profiles at the

weld interface are plotted in Fig. 7. The wood and silicon rubber, which could generally be considered as good insulating materials for this purpose, gave expected results that corresponded with the experimental data. The steel insulation graph, on the other hand, revealed that the desired welding temperature could not be reached with these welding parameters. Furthermore, at this power level the welding temperature was impossible to reach at all, due to the thermal properties of steel, which in this configuration presented a heat sink that prevented the welding to be completed. This led to the conclusion that the temperature distribution in the weld is very sensitive to the type of insulation used. It was also concluded that when studying or applying the resistance welding process, it is necessary to determine the optimal welding parameters for every different welding configuration.

The influence of the insulating material was also addressed with respect to its thickness. Three cases with different thickness of the insulation block were simulated. Previously described welding configuration (with wood as insulation material) and welding

Fig. 8: The influence of the thickness of the wooden insulation material on the thermal profiles in the weld.

parameters were used. Temperature profiles at the weld interface and at the top of the laminate for insulation thickness of 35, 10 and 2.5 mm are plotted in Fig. 8. The results revealed that the thickness of the insulation has almost negligible influence on the temperature distribution in the welded material. Only when the insulation thickness approached the thickness of the welded laminate (2.5 mm), more significant temperature difference was predicted, especially in the cooling profile. In this case, due to its relatively small volume, the temperature of the insulation block during heat-up approached that of the laminate top surface, which significantly limits its capability to accept the excessive heat from the laminate, diminishing by that its cooling capacity. As a result, a uniform temperature through the laminate thickness was reached a short time after the beginning of the cooling phase.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermal analysis of the resistance welding process of thermoplastic composites has been performed using a finite element transient heat transfer model of the welding process. The geometry of the model was based on the standard DCB welding configuration that was used for obtaining the experimental data that were compared to the model predictions. The model

predictions showed a good correlation with the experimental data. The influence of the material properties on the temperature profiles was investigated in the first part of the study. The temperature profiles through the weld thickness of the glass fibre and carbon fibre laminates were compared. It was concluded that composite materials with low transversal heat conductivity offer the opportunity of local heat-up in the vicinity of the heating element, especially for high power levels, while materials with higher transversal conductivity, on the other hand, provide more uniform heating of the bulk material.

The thermal aspects of the edge effect phenomenon have been comprehensively studied in this thermal analysis. The influence of the composite material properties and welding parameters on the temperature distribution have been investigated, as well as the influence of the edge effect on the maximum weld length. It was concluded that the edge effect in itself does not restrict the welding area (welding length), because it affects only the temperature in a limited area in the vicinity of the weld edges. The thermal gradients that it produces at the edges can however, under certain conditions prevent the completion of the weld.

The influence of the insulation material has been studied with respect to the material type and thickness. It was concluded that the temperature distribution in the weld is very sensitive to the type of insulation used, which implied the need to determine the optimal welding parameters for every different welding configuration. It was also concluded that the thickness of the insulation material has almost negligible influence on the temperature distribution in the welded material, except for extreme cases when very thin insulation is applied.

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